

5-SHO‘BA TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH

TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE INTRODUCTION OF PROGRAM AND METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING FOR FUTURE ENERGY ENGINEERS

Eshonkulov Bunyod Saydullayevich

Teacher of the Department of Applied Mathematics of the Jizzakh branch of the
National University of Uzbekistan

bunyodebs@mail.ru

Annotation: This article addresses the issue of a technological approach to the training of future energy engineers for professional activities based on digital technologies. This article can be used by those involved in the introduction of the technological approach method.

Keywords: program-methodical; digital; energetic; engineer; technology; development; components; educational activities; model; organizational and structural; improvement; strategy.

It is known that in the educational process or in the process of training in a specialty, it is necessary to use different approaches to achieve a particular goal, and such approaches require the development of new methods and techniques. However, such a method or rules should also be able to serve to optimize the solution to the problem at hand. Therefore, the method (method) to be developed (or selected) should be aimed at finding the optimal solution to the problem.

This article also discusses the problem of developing an optimal option for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies.

It is known that the current opportunities of science, technology and pedagogical innovations in all spheres of life require the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital educational technologies. and should also ensure that their intellectual potential is constantly evolving.

The results of our research in this area allow us to describe an innovative methodology developed to improve the software for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies. We expressed it as follows:

Systematic implementation of educational activities (measures, efforts) to improve the software for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of a pre-established plan, as an innovative method of improving the software for

training future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies a set of methods, techniques and technologies.

This means that the training of future energy engineers on the basis of this innovative methodology is an innovative process, which can improve (innovate, inform, modernize) the training of future professionals in accordance with modern requirements. Therefore, we found it expedient to put this innovative methodology into practice [1-5].

The results of our research in this area show that a technological approach to solving such problems will be needed. The reason for this is that technology is a conscious, creative activity related to creativity, which consists of a series of efforts (educational activities) to achieve pre-determined (planned) goals. The innovative methodology developed for the introduction of software for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies is also a technological approach to the training of future professionals, and it is a continuous process that reflects the planned results of training future energy engineers. Therefore, it will be possible to improve the training of future energy engineers on the basis of the components of the technological approach in this process and the methods, techniques and technologies that create the laws of their relationship. In this case, the importance of software and software, and software is an important technological component of training future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies.

The following were considered as components of the technological approach for the implementation of the developed methodology for improving the software and methodological preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital technologies:

- **Digital technology opportunities.** At the same time, the requirements for the development of digital technologies are studied analytically, on the basis of which the issue of scientific and methodological substantiation of the possibilities of preparing digital educational technologies and software-didactic software is solved;

- **Stages of preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity.** At the same time, the directions of improving the preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies and their modernization, as well as scientific and methodological substantiation of their algorithmic stages; formation of the updated educational content on preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies and definition of methods, forms and means of training on them; Development of a methodology for creating software for the preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital

technologies and the corresponding intelligent training system; Development of criteria for identifying and evaluating the pedagogical effectiveness of the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies and the development of methodological recommendations based on them;

- **Algorithmic stages of preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies.** It is scientifically and methodologically based from the research point of view of the stages of preparation, formation, substantiation and introduction of preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity;

- **Organizational and structural model for the development of scientific and methodological support for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies.** At the same time, on the basis of didactic, educational-methodical, educational-software, educational-informational support of professional energy engineers training of future energy engineers methodical, professional and social knowledge and development of methods and technologies to improve the educational activity of future energy engineers the issue will be the main focus;

- **scientific and methodological substantiation of the general view of improving the software for the preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital technologies.** At the same time, digital educational technologies, application software packages, pedagogical software, intelligent systems, intelligent learning systems, interactive work programs, etc. will be developed to address the problem and based on them, software and methodological improvements will be designed;

- **scientific and methodological substantiation of the stages of improving the software and methodological preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities.** At the same time, an organizational and structural model of training future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies will be developed; the updated educational content on training of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies will be formed; a set of tools used in the process of improving the software for the preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital technologies; on the basis of digital technologies will be developed technologies for the preparation of updated software and methodological training of future energy engineers for professional activities, etc;

- **scientific and methodological substantiation of the strategy for improving the software and methodological preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities.** This includes planning efforts for the

preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities; formation of a database on professional training of future energy engineers; substantiation of the mechanism of creation of software and methodical preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies; designing activities to prepare future energy engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital technologies; substantiation of the dynamics of the stages of preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies; substantiate the practical importance of software for the preparation of future energy engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital technologies; Preliminary examination of software and methodical training of future energy engineers for professional activity on the basis of digital technologies; evaluate and summarize the results obtained; issues of developing a system of recommendations for further improvement of professional training of future energy engineers;

- **scientific and methodological substantiation of software components and related laws.** In this case, the didactic capabilities of pedagogical software and the justification of their set; a package of applications and a set of interactive working programs will be prepared; innovative software-didactic complex is prepared for research; prepares software for public use; an interactive training complex will be prepared; algorithmic stages of training are scientifically and methodologically based;

- **substantiate didactic support for the training of future energy engineers.** In this case, the following types of supplies will be prepared: educational and didactic; educational and methodical; educational software and educational information;

- **identify and evaluate the results achieved.** At the same time, work is carried out to identify and evaluate the results achieved and compare them with the requirements of the state educational standard;

- **Development of a methodology to improve the software for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies.** At the same time, the main blocks of improving the required methodological support and the mechanism of their operation will be developed: didactic support block; software block; adaptation block and identification blocks;

- **identify and justify the source to be studied.** In this case, the study of a particular science (topic), a concept (law, rule), the principles of teaching are considered;

- **analytical substantiation of the final stage of development of innovative methodology.** At the same time, work will be carried out to identify

and evaluate the results of the implementation of innovative methods, summarize and form a system of recommendations.

As can be seen from the components of the technological approach to the practical application of innovative methods of improving the software for training future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies, the implementation of the developed innovative methods requires a unique creative approach.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the introduction of software for the training of future energy engineers on the basis of digital technologies provides ample opportunities for scientific and methodological justification of the object of technological research and research strategy. There will be ample opportunities for the practical use of interactive training complexes in the training of future energy engineers on the basis of algorithmic stages of training and digital educational technologies.

The innovative technological approach, designed to improve the training of future professionals, has a methodological character. Therefore, it can be used not only in the training of future energy engineers, but also in other areas of intellectual professional activity.

References:

1. Turakulov O.X., Eshankulov B.S., Jabborov U., Hafizov E. Formation of informational educational environment. *Ilkogretim Online – Elementary Education Online*, Year 2021, – №4: – pp. 1938-1944.

2. Turakulov O.X., Savurbaev A., Eshankulov B.S., Akhmedov J.R. Digitization of the information educational environment: problems and solutions // *Scientific-theoretical and methodical journal of pedagogical skills*. – Bukhara, 2021, – pp. 20-24.

3. Turakulov O.X., Eshankulov B.S. Development of scientific and methodological support for the preparation of future power engineers for professional activities on the basis of digital technologies // *Scientific-methodical journal "Oriental art and culture": Conference on Science and Education in Uzbekistan*. – Fergana, 2020, – pp. 14-17.

4. Eshankulov B.S. Algorithmic stages of preparation of future energy engineers for professional activity // *Reforms in the system of vocational education: Innovative ideas in the field of professional development. Proceedings of the international scientific-practical conference*. – T., 2020, – P. 392-395.

5. Eshankulov B.S. Creation of educational content that is suitable for modeling the training of future specialists on the basis of digital technologies // *“Berlin Studies” – Transnational journal of science and humanities*. – Germany, 2021, – pp. 562-568.